

MANUFACTURING AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF Ti/APC-2 HYBRID COMPOSITE LAMINATES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

M.-H. R. Jen*, Y.-C. Sung and C.-W Liou

Dept. of Mechanical and Electro-Mechanical Engr. National Sun Yat-Sen University
No.70, Lianhai Rd., Gushan District, Kaohsiung 80424, Taiwan, R.O.C.

*jmhr@mail.nsysu.edu.tw

SUMMARY

The Ti/APC-2 hybrid cross-ply composite laminates were fabricated. Their mechanical response due to static tensile and constant stress amplitude tension-tension at elevated temperatures was investigated. From test results the samples by the pretreatment of anodic method possess higher resistance than those by mechanical polishing method.

Keywords: Hybrid composite laminate, Titanium sheet, APC-2, Fatigue, Elevated temperature.

ABSTRACT

Anodic oxidation method is a commonly used surface treatment on titanium alloys. However, the bonding of polymer composites to titanium is still a problem, which has not been fully solved. In order to improve the bonding capabilities adhesive properties, many surface treatments have been studied and discussed [1-2]. Based on the experience of successfully manufacturing Mg/APC-2 and Al/APC-2 nanocomposite laminates [3], and the PEEK matrix can sustain its mechanical properties up to 423K [4], the Ti/CF/PEEK composite laminates might be utilized at higher temperatures. Herein, the mechanical properties subjected to tensile and the cyclic tests at elevated temperatures were obtained. The failure mechanisms were observed. The response of mechanical behavior was highlighted.

The unidirectional AS-4/PEEK prepregs were cut and stacked into cross-ply [0/90]_s laminates. Prior to lamination, two surface treatments of titanium sheets had been chosen. However, after a series of fatigue tests, the samples by mechanical polishing found poor bonding and noticeable delamination occurred after 10⁴ cycles. The samples by chromic acid anodic method were found much better as demonstrated.

The longitudinal stiffness and ultimate tensile strength of Ti/APC-2 cross-ply composite laminates at elevated temperatures were plotted in Figure 1. It was obvious to see that the mechanical properties by anodic method were better than those by mechanical polishing. A nanoscale columnar and porous oxide uniform layer has been taken by SEM as shown in Figure 2. Then, the stress vs. cycles (S-N) curves by two different pretreatments of titanium sheet were received due to T-T fatigue tests at elevated temperatures as shown in Figure 3. It is reasonable to see the curves go downwards as

temperature rising. Importantly, the S-N curves of samples due to electroplating of Ti sheets were found higher resistance to cyclic loading and no delaminations were observed at a million cycles.

Figure 1. The (a) longitudinal stiffness and (b) ultimate strength of Ti/APC-2 cross-ply composite at elevated temperatures with both surface treatments of Ti sheets.

Figure 2. SEM image of oxide layer on the titanium surface from chromic acid anodic method.

Figure 3. The S-N curves of Ti/APC-2 cross-ply composite laminates by both surface treatments of titanium sheets at elevated temperatures.

References

- 1 G. W. Critchlow and D. M. Brewis, Review of surface pretreatments for titanium alloys, *Int. J. Adhesion and Adhesives* 15, p 161-172, 1995.
- 2 P. Molitor, V. Barron and T. Young, Surface treatment of titanium for adhesive bonding to polymer composites: a review, *Int. J. Adhesion and Adhesives* 21, p 129-136, 2001.
- 3 M.-H. R. Jen, Y.-C. Tseng and P.-Y. Li, Fatigue response of hybrid magnesium/carbon-fiber/PEEK nanocomposite laminates at elevated temperature, *Journal of JSEM*, Vol. 7, Special Issue, pp. 56-60, 2007.
- 4 T. E. Attwood, P. C. Dawson, L. J. Freeman, L. R. J. Hoy, J. B. Rose and P. A. Staniland, Synthesis and properties of polyaryletherketones, *Polymer* 22, p 1096-1103, 1981.